

Public Library and Tribal Society Development

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Introduction

A public library is generally understood as a library run by the people for the people. It is mostly true. According to the aspects of the various functions of public libraries that are important to the experts, they have described them in different ways and in different words. e.g. Some people think that public library is an information center, while some people think that public library is an institution that provides useful information in various fields of life. These are all the characteristics of a real public library. Because the public library is a democratic social institution providing education, culture and information the thoughts of man, his ideas and the literature created by his own talent are collected and preserved in such libraries and made available to the public.

Definition:

It was defined by UNESCO in 1949 as broad enough to include all qualities and characteristics of public libraries. In the year 1962, it was revised chronologically and made accurate. He has announced it in his advertisement.

It is a public library as follows –

1. A large part of the expenditure is collected from public funds.
2. The library is open door and provides free library services to readers of all castes and religions without any discrimination.
3. The nature of a library is like a voluntary educational institution. There is a performance of continuous education.
4. Readers are provided with maximum information on various subjects, without prejudice. For this, various educational information providing tools are integrated. Various social and cultural activities are undertaken. This definition includes certain basic guidelines.

Information center-

Public library should not be only a place of entertainment but also an important center for obtaining information. In today's age of science where life is fast paced, readers need to get new information in various fields. That information should be true, absolute and objective. It should not be wrong, partial, outdated and biased. Collection, acquisition, preservation and free distribution of such money to the needy should be done without delay. Just as this process involves the flow of information,

so does its philosophy of democracy. Readers have the right to ask for information and it is the duty of public libraries to do so.

Centers of Self-Education-

Educational institutes provide education in limited subjects during certain periods and accordingly their libraries provide knowledge materials to their readers. Man is an animal who cultivates many hobbies and takes interest in many subjects. Even after the completion of the student phase, he is still acquiring knowledge, taking the information he can get, reading and studying. Trying to master the

subject of interest. At such times public libraries are very useful and can fulfill a great educational responsibility. That is why the public library becomes the center of self-learning.

Center for cultural enrichment –

Books work to develop human consciousness and provide knowledge and pleasure in his spare time. It includes poetry, drama, music composition, sculpture, dance, painting like Gandha literature. All these things refine the mind and intellect and bring a kind of cultural glory to man. Public libraries protect the local cultural heritage of the area. It is made available there according to the needs of the readers. is provided there. It is also a learning centre, information center and cultural centre. It is a very necessary organization in democracy and its nature is charitable and enlightening.

Tribal welfare programs:

Under the British rule, the tribals and their oppression became severe. However, the policy of the British rulers towards the tribal community was negative. That is, the British policy was that no interference should be made in the affairs of the British until the tribal tribes did not become a hindrance in the administration of the British. Thus, despite the neglect of tribal development, the welfare program of Indian tribals was started during this period. Development of tribals is a welfare program for them

Many voluntary organizations and activists started trying for tribal welfare. Thus, the tribal welfare efforts which started in the pre-independence period gained more momentum in the post-independence period. A detailed overview of tribal welfare program can be taken as follows.

Tribal welfare programs in pre-independence period:

We can distinguish two main types of tribal welfare programs namely tribal welfare programs at government level and tribal welfare programs at non-governmental level. While considering the tribal welfare program in the pre-independence era, one has to think only about the tribal program at the non-governmental level. Because the British never took a positive stance to solve the problems of the tribals. Despite realizing the complexity of tribal issues, the policy of the British rulers was negative. As a result, it has to be said that the tribal welfare program at the government level started in the post-independence era.

In the pre-independence era, the tribal issues were not given special attention as the main objective was to make the country independent. It has to be admitted that some Christian missionaries did remarkable work for tribal welfare during the pre-independence era. Also, taking inspiration from Mahatma Gandhi, many social reformers have contributed to solve the problems of tribals. E.g. A.D. In 1922 K. Thakkarvappa established the organization 'Bhill Seva' in Gujarat and 'Bhill Seva Mandal' was established in Khandesh. At the same time, the work done by Mrs. Godutai Parulekar to solve the problems of tribals is remarkable. Briefly, in the pre-independence era, sporadic attempts were made to solve tribal problems at the mortal level. Due to the lack of financial support from the government, it is natural that the tribal welfare efforts at the non-governmental level are very limited.

Constitutional Provisions for Protection of Tribals:

Tribal Enterara to National Leaders During Freedom Movement

During the period before the establishment of the pass, the issue of tribals only: there were sporadic attempts at the kari level. Due to the lack of financial support from the government, it was natural that the tribal welfare efforts at the non-governmental level were very limited. Constitutional Provisions for the Protection of Tribals The national leaders of the time of the independence movement were certainly aware of the complexity of tribal issues. It was clear that without special efforts to protect the tribal tribes, it was not possible to stop the unknowing attack of the advanced society on them. Therefore, while framing the Constitution of India, some provisions were made for the protection of tribal tribes. The constitutional provisions for the protection of tribals are as follows.

1. Certain provisions of the Indian Constitution grant any tribal person equal status with ordinary Indian citizens. E.g. There shall be no

discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, gender, place of birth. This provision has been made in Article 15 of the Constitution. Also, according to Article 16 of the Constitution, there will be no discrimination in government jobs. ie the common Indian According to the principle of equal opportunity, the tribal person has been accorded independent rights equal to other Indian persons. According to the 19th article of the constitution, everyone has got freedom of conduct, thought, speech, business and communication anywhere in the country, disposal of wealth etc. Thus certain provisions of the Indian Constitution provide tribal persons with all manner of equality with other citizens. In other words, the Constitution guarantees equal treatment to all persons including tribals in India in all places like educational institutions, public parks, hospitals, hostels etc.

2. The Indian tribals were completely trapped in the financial exploitation by moneylenders, contractors and landlords to free them from the following special provisions in the constitution. According to Article 23 of the Constitution, forced labour, prostitution, unethical trade in persons etc. have been made illegal. It is because of these provisions that the government has been able to free many tribal persons and tribal families from the vagrancy.
3. There is a lot of diversity in terms of languages, festivals, customs and culture of tribal tribes. Tribals are very few in number. Despite this, according to the 25th and 22nd article of the constitution, individuals have got religious freedom. Also their educational and cultural rights have been protected. Thus, it is only because of these constitutional provisions that it is possible to protect the culture of the tribal tribes, which are small in number.
4. Development of these tribes is not possible unless tribals get proper representation in democratic governance. For this, some seats have been reserved for tribal representatives in the Lok Sabha and in the Legislative Assemblies of the constituent states on the basis of population. In other words, the provisions of reserved or protected constituencies have made it possible for the Adivasi representative to express the tribal people's opinion in the Constituent Assembly and the Lok Sabha.
5. The tribal population is very high in the three constituent states of Orissa, Bihar and Madhya Pradesh. Therefore, it has been provided in accordance with Article 165 of the Constitution that an independent Minister for Tribal Welfare and Development should be appointed in any cabinet in the three constituent states. In every

case, generally in the constituent states where the number of tribal tribes is large, one minister belongs to the tribal tribe in the cabinet of all such constituent states. Also, the Union Cabinet usually includes at least one tribal person. Thus the tribals in the government The system of representation shows that indirect transactions have been created in all the constituent states of India.

6. Under Article 338 of the Constitution of India, the President can appoint officers for the protection of Scheduled Tribes.
7. The number of tribal tribes is very high in Assam and the region around Assam i.e. North East India. Keeping in mind that the nature of the problems of these tribes is also complicated, the following special provision has been made in the constitution. The tribal area of Assam can be divided into two parts. One is an autonomous district and the other is an autonomous region. These autonomous districts will have 'Zilla Committees' and autonomous areas will have 'Area Committees'. These committees have been given the right to make laws regarding land, forest, agriculture, property, marriage and other social issues and the work of justice has also been entrusted to this committee. Whether or not ordinary Acts of Parliament apply to this area will also depend on the opinion of the committee. Thus, as per the 5th Schedule of Article 244, a separate arrangement has been made for the administration of tribal areas. A provision has been made to appoint a tribal advisory board to advise the governor for tribal welfare in the state having tribal tribes in Patne.
8. According to Article 335 of the Constitution of India, some seats have been reserved for the tribal candidates in the government service and the age limit condition has been relaxed for them to enter the job.
9. It is clear from the constitutional provisions for the welfare of the tribals that the constitution has entrusted the government with the responsibility of bringing about educational, economic and social reforms among the tribals. Special provisions have been made in the constitution so that the government can solve the serious problems of the tribals in the area of Madhya Pradesh and Assam in North East India. Due to the constitutional provisions it can be said that the role of the government in the tribal welfare program becomes the most important.

Role of Government in Tribal Welfare Program

Constitutional Responsibility:- The provisions of the Indian Constitution on tribal welfare make it the responsibility of the government to formulate and

implement the tribal welfare programme. No matter which political party the government is in power, every ruling government has to fulfill its constitutional responsibility. It can be said that tribal welfare programs are the responsibility of the government system at all three levels namely central government, unit state government and state institutions.

Some schemes for Adi Gali welfare are prepared by the central government while some schemes are prepared by the state governments. Governments at both levels have to allocate financial funds to implement tribal welfare programmes. Come to the administration system in local bodies Financial subsidy is also given for the implementation of the program. In short, due to the policies of the ruling political party, the prejudice towards tribals as weak, and the foresight of the leaders, tribal welfare programs are not being prepared; So they are created and implemented to fulfill the constitutional responsibility. Nature of tribal welfare program prepared by the government: Crores of rupees have been spent for tribal welfare program from the first five year plan to the tenth five year plan. The tribal welfare program implemented in the post-independence era can be explained as follows.

1. Education:- Many vested interests take advantage of the ignorance of tribals. Their extraordinary ignorance is the most important reason for their miserable life. That is why education has been given special importance and priority in their welfare program. It is the main duty of the welfare state organization to provide many educational benefits to the tribals. The concessions created for tribals can be described as follows.

With the aim of providing education to the new generation of tribals and at the same time creating facilities for their professional education, ashram schools were established in the tribal department. Apart from primary education, various professions like agriculture, spinning, weaving are also being taught in these schools. The cost of food, cloth etc. of the students in this school is paid by the government. In Maharashtra, ashram schools are run by private institutions. They are given subsidy by the government. Electrical and mechanical engineering education is given in ashram schools in Bihar, Manipur area. In Assam, Bihar, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, technical education schools have also been opened for the tribals along with ashram schools. The number of orphanages and technical schools is being increased by making provisions in every five-year plan.

The government has planned to give scholarships to the tribal students so that they can meet the expenses of books, clothes, lunch etc. till the examination in the schools. This scheme is implemented in all the

constituent states. For this, the government is providing a large amount of money.

In order to provide higher education to the tribals, the government is implementing a scheme to provide scholarships to the tribal students who are pursuing lifelong education. The scholarship amount of tribal students is also increased from time to time. In order to prepare the tribal students for the competitive examination conducted by the Public Service Commission, the government has established special guidance institutions for the tribal candidates. In order to facilitate the admission of tribal students in various educational institutions, some reserved seats have been kept for them in the educational institutions.

1. In admissions for Asian students to be admitted to educational institutions

Multi-Disciplinary Research Journal / Vol 5 percent discount is also given to them if they meet the eligibility criteria.

2. Tribal Welfare:- From this discussion it is clear that special emphasis is being laid in the tribal welfare program to increase the level of education in the tribal society. Also due to this, the level of literacy in tribal society has increased than before. Due to scholarship, the literacy rate in the tribal society has increased more than before. The number of tribal students pursuing education has increased due to the scholarship scheme and the number of these students is increasing every year.

3. Economic development: Agriculture, cottage industries, cooperative societies, housing schemes etc. are included in the tribal welfare program for the economic upliftment of tribals. Agriculture has been given priority in tribal welfare programme. Because the occupation of majority of tribals is agriculture.

Agricultural land is being made available as a benefit of sustainable agriculture. The Maximum Retention of Agricultural Land Act means that tribals are given priority in allotment of agricultural land received by the government from the ceiling. The government has passed a law to prevent the transfer of tribal agricultural land. According to this law, transactions related to sale, donation, mortgage and contract of land owned by tribals cannot be done by non-tribals.

Many pilot schemes are being implemented by the central government to improve the farming practices of tribals. The result of this scheme is that more than 400 tribal families in Madhya Pradesh, Tripura, Bihar, Orissa have started farming. In short, through Panchayat Samiti, tribal farmers are being encouraged to practice modern farming. For this, chemical fertilizers, seeds, small implements required for agriculture are being made available to tribal farmers at low cost. Cottage industry is a complementary industry to agriculture. Therefore,

in the five-year plan, emphasis is being laid on the cottage industries of tribals. The government has made special provisions for tribals to know the modern techniques of cottage industries, to make the manufactured goods available in the market and to get financial assistance for the growth of trade. Weaving, sewing, basket making, rope twisting etc. are being taught. Loan facility is being provided for cottage industries. In every five-year plan, financial provision is being made on a regular basis for the development of tribal cottage industries. E.g. Tents were reserved for the second five-year Yoj Tol Kuti Yoga. Out of Rs.5.74 crores, Rs.2.56 crores would be reserved for Adi Gasi Chitirudyogy.

Animal Husbandry, Poultry Husbandry, Pig Husbandry are specially made by the government for tribals to do. Emphasis is being laid on creation of cooperative credit funds to provide financial support to tribal small scale industries. In various states of India, tribals have been waived on their loans till date. Loans with low interest rates are being made available to tribals for agriculture and small scale industries. From this discussion, it is clear that the government is making great efforts for the development of tribal cottage industries. A special emphasis has been laid in the tribal welfare program to create cooperative societies for the economic development of tribals. Due to various forms of exploitation of tribals, ignorance of the provisions of law and restrictions imposed on tribals by the Forest Act, the need for cooperative societies of tribals in the forest department became acutely felt. Co-operative societies of tribals have been formed in many states including Maharashtra. For this purpose, the government has provided 14 crore rupees and more than 1000 cooperative societies are working for tribals.

Garan started to feel intense. Co-operative societies of tribals have been formed in many states including Maharashtra. For this, the government has provided Rs. 14 crores and more than 1000 cooperative societies are working for tribals. Bibliography Balekar Rs. :

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